

Minimum Age of Criminal Responsibility in Brunei Darussalam: A Comparative Doctrinal Analysis

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Abstract

The minimum age of criminal responsibility (MACR) refers to the lowest age at which a child can be held legally accountable for alleged criminal offences. Upon reaching this age, a child may be deemed capable of bearing criminal liability. It is a standard principle in all criminal justice systems that youthful immaturity can negate criminal responsibility. Article 40(3)(a) of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) obliges States Parties to establish “a minimum age below which children shall be presumed not to have the capacity to infringe the penal law.” In Brunei Darussalam, the MACR is governed by both section 82 and section 83 of the Penal Code (Cap. 22), as well as section 12 and section 13 of the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275). This paper aims to examine the doctrinal foundations and implications of the current MACR in Brunei Darussalam, in comparison with international standards and selected jurisdictions. A doctrinal legal approach with comparative elements is adopted. The paper concludes that, due to Brunei Darussalam’s dual criminal justice system, the MACR is governed under two parallel legal frameworks. This may result in inconsistencies in age thresholds. The paper recommends the harmonisation of the MACR across both systems. The paper also recommends the codification of the Syariah concepts of *tamyiz* (discernment) and *baligh* (puberty) to ensure legal clarity and consistency.

Keywords: *Brunei Darussalam, child, minimum age of criminal responsibility, Penal Code, Syariah Penal Code.*

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Introduction

One of the most complex, contested, and controversial issues facing modern juvenile and youth justice systems is the minimum age of criminal responsibility (MACR) — the age at which a child is considered sufficiently mature to be held accountable under the substantive criminal law (Church et. al, 2013). It is a standard principle in all criminal justice systems that youthful immaturity can negate criminal responsibility. The MACR is the lowest age at which children in each country can be prosecuted in any court and is therefore a fundamental concern for the protection of children’s rights and juvenile justice (South Asia and the Minimum Age of Criminal Responsibility, 2005). Article 40(3)(a) of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) obliges States Parties to establish “a minimum age below which children shall be presumed not to have the capacity to infringe the penal law.” In Brunei Darussalam, the MACR is governed by both section 82 and section 83 of the Penal Code (Cap. 22), as well as section 12 and section 13 of the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275). The sections mandate that the acts committed by a child without attaining sufficient majority of understanding to judge the nature and consequences of his conduct on that occasion should not be considered an offence.

This paper undertakes an examination of the doctrinal foundations and implications of the existing MACR in Brunei Darussalam, with reference to international standards and selected comparative jurisdictions. The analysis employs a doctrinal legal methodology supplemented by comparative elements. The paper is divided into four main parts, excluding the introduction. The first part examines the legal framework in Brunei Darussalam concerning the MACR. This discussion is particularly important given Brunei Darussalam’s dual criminal justice system, under which two parallel legal frameworks govern the MACR—potentially leading to inconsistencies in age thresholds. The second part addresses international legal standards, focusing on Brunei Darussalam’s obligations under international law. This section is essential for assessing the extent to which domestic laws align with global norms. The third part presents a comparative analysis of the MACR, covering ASEAN and other regional jurisdictions, common law and civil law systems, as well as perspectives under Islamic law. This comparative approach is especially relevant considering the country’s dual criminal justice system. The fourth part sets out the conclusion and offers recommendations for the operation of the MACR in Brunei Darussalam.

The Legal Framework in Brunei Darussalam

The legal framework in Brunei Darussalam is characterised by its unique dual structure, which harmoniously blends Islamic law, known as Syariah, with common law practices inherited from its colonial past (Generis Global Legal Services, 2024). This duality is indicative of the nation’s commitment to both religious principles and contemporary legal frameworks, allowing for a comprehensive and adaptable approach to governance and justice (Generis Global Legal Services, 2024). At the heart of Brunei Darussalam’s legal system lies the principle of justice, which emphasises fair treatment and the protection of individual rights. Justice in Brunei Darussalam is pursued through both Islamic teachings and established common law, ensuring that all legal matters are addressed comprehensively (Generis Global Legal Services, 2024). This dual commitment is further upheld by the judiciary, which is expected to operate with impartiality, maintaining a careful balance between Islamic values and secular legal standards. It is, therefore, essential to understand that the legal framework of Brunei Darussalam cannot be fully comprehended without considering the country’s historical development, which has resulted in a unique blend of the English common law system and Syariah law operating concurrently. Consequently, the MACR cannot be examined in isolation without acknowledging this distinctive legal context.

Common Law Influence and Local Legislation

The influence of English common law in the legal framework of Brunei Darussalam cannot be fully understood without reference to the Application of Laws Act 1951 (Cap. 2). This pivotal statute provides that English common law, along with the doctrines of equity and statutes of general application as they

existed in England prior to April 25, 1951, shall also be in force in Brunei Darussalam. This Act serves as the gateway for the reception of English common law in the country. However, this is subject to the important proviso that such common law, equity doctrines, and statutes shall apply only subject to the local circumstances and customs. Consequently, the Brunei Penal Code (Cap. 22) incorporates elements of English common law. For instance, the doctrines of *doli incapax* and *doli capax*, which originate from English common law, have been codified respectively in sections 82 and 83 of the Penal Code.

Criminal Responsibility under the Penal Code (Cap. 22)

The issue of the MACR in Brunei Darussalam cannot be examined without reference to the Penal Code (Cap. 22). Section 82 stipulates that no act constitutes an offence if committed by a child under 7 years of age. In contrast, section 83 provides that an act committed by a child aged between 7 and 12 years does not constitute an offence if the child has not attained sufficient maturity of understanding to judge the nature and consequences of their conduct on that occasion.

By virtue of section 82 above, it is crucial to note that the provision assumes that a child under the age of 7 years cannot commit a crime and therefore cannot be held liable for a crime. A child under the age of 7 years is *doli incapax* and therefore receives absolute immunity. It is believed that a child under the age of 7 years cannot distinguish between right and wrong. He does not have the mental capacity to understand the nature and the consequences of his actions. This assumption is clear and cannot be denied because the child cannot understand the effects of his actions. This provision exempts a child under the age of 7 years from all criminal liability, regardless of how serious the crime is.

Section 82 embodies the conclusive presumption which admits no contradiction that a child under 7 years of age cannot commit a crime. The fact that the child is below 7 years of age is ipso facto an answer to any prosecution, and it is not open to the prosecution to rebut this by leading evidence on the intellect or cleverness of the child. Thus, under the age of 7 years, a child is presumed by law to be incapable of committing a crime. This presumption is conclusive, irrebuttable presumption of law and the defence is absolute (Yeo et. al, 2018).

As for section 83, it assumes that a child over 7 years old but under 12 years is *doli capax*, i.e., able to commit crimes according to his maturity level. Under section 83, it clearly states that crimes committed by a child above the age of 7 years and under the age of 12 years, in such cases, the court will to the level of understanding and prescribe the knowledge of a child related to such activity, which means that the court will try to examine and identify whether the child has enough capacity to understand the nature and scope of the consequences of his particular actions. The effects related to the behavioural part would lead to criminal consequences, we cannot stimulate it into the normal activity of behaving.

Under section 83, the immunity given to a child within this age group is conditional upon the child not being of sufficient maturity of understanding to judge the nature and the consequences of his conduct. To escape criminal liability, the child should not know the natural and physical consequences of his conduct. The phrase “nature and consequences of his conduct” in section 83 does not refer to the penal consequences of the offence. The phrase means the natural consequences which flow from a voluntary act, such as for instance, when fire is applied to an inflammable substance, it will burn, or that a heavy blow with an axe or sword will cause death or grievous hurt (*Queen v Lukhini Agradanini* (1874)).

Based on sections 82 and 83 above, it is crucial to note that the Brunei Penal Code stipulates 7 to be the age of attainment of criminal responsibility but children between 7 and below 12 who have not shown sufficient maturity may be absolved from criminality as well, on another extreme, should a child between 7 and 12 be charged; he may invoke “infancy” as a defence. Hence, children between the age of 7 to 12 years old and children above the age of 12 are treated as adults for the purpose of criminal responsibility, while children of this last category, namely children above 12, are treated as adults for the purposes of criminal responsibility regardless of the nature of the crime although treated differently in terms of criminal procedure and the disposals available to the court.

Having addressed sections 82 and 83 of the Penal Code (Cap. 22), the crucial issue that arises is whether reform is necessary regarding the current age brackets. It is undeniable that advancements in technology

and the rapid development of information technology have exposed children to a wide range of violent content. This raises the question: should Brunei Darussalam continue to uphold the irrebuttable presumption that a child under the age of seven cannot commit a crime? Furthermore, should the current minimum age of criminal responsibility—set at 7 years—be revised to better reflect the realities of today’s environment? The concluding section of this paper addresses these questions, incorporating them into the recommendations for legal reform.

Criminal Responsibility under the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275)

Brunei Darussalam’s criminal justice system permits the concurrent operation of the Penal Code (Cap. 22) and the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275). Where charges are pursued under the Penal Code, jurisdiction rests with the civil criminal courts. Conversely, charges brought under the Syariah Penal Code fall within the jurisdiction of the Syariah courts. In the context of the MACR, it is, therefore, necessary to examine sections 12 and 13 of the Syariah Penal Code. Section 12 provides that no act constitutes an offence if committed by a child who is not *mumaiyiz* (i.e., a child who has not yet reached the age of discernment or the ability to differentiate between right and wrong). Section 13 further states that a *mumaiyiz* child who has not attained the status of *baligh* (i.e., the age of puberty) cannot be subjected to *hadd* or *qisas* punishments for offences carrying such penalties, though other forms of punishments may be imposed.

For a proper understanding of sections 12 and 13 of the Syariah Penal Code, it is necessary to examine the definitions of the terms “*mumaiyiz*” and “*baligh*.” Pursuant to section 3(1) of the Syariah Courts Evidence Order 2001, “*baligh*” denotes a person who has attained the age of puberty in accordance with *Hukum Syara*, whereas “*mumaiyiz*” refers to a child who has reached the stage at which they are capable of distinguishing between matters.

Attaining *baligh* is one of the indicators of a person’s intellectual maturity. A child’s *baligh* status may be determined either naturally, through customary practices, or by setting a maximum age for its attainment. The appearance of physiological signs signifies that the child has entered the stage of adulthood, indicating readiness for independent decision-making and sound judgment. The physical signs for boys include experiencing *al-ihtilam*, the emission of seminal fluid, and while for girls, it is the onset of menstruation (Noor, 2013). Being *baligh* and possessing mature judgment is among the prerequisites for a person to have *abluyyatu al-ada al-kamilah*, which denotes eligibility to perform all religious obligations that can affect the legality, permissibility, prohibition, or validity of a matter (Samsudin et. al, 2023). The other two components are the ability to understand and to make decisions. Therefore, it is important to note that criminal acts committed by children are not considered offences until they have reached the age of *baligh*. In the absence of physical signs of *baligh*—such as the emission of seminal fluid or the onset of menstruation—the age threshold for *baligh* will be applied. Islamic jurists (*fuqaha*) hold differing opinions on how this age should be determined. Abdul Qader Audah suggested that children typically experience a dream indicating *baligh* before age 15 (Samsudin et. al, 2023). Imam Nawawi and Umar ibn Abdul Aziz also adhered to age 15 as the age of *baligh* for an individual, delineating between childhood and adulthood (Samsudin et. al, 2023). Next, Imam Abu Hanifah set 18 as the age of *baligh* for boys and 17 for girls. Meanwhile, Imam Malik designated 18 as the age of *baligh* for both boys and girls (Yusuf & Rahman, 2014). The age of 18 is supported by only a minority of scholars. On the other hand, another viewpoint asserted that all three Hanafi, Shafi’i, and Hanbali schools define the age of *baligh* for children as 15. Only the Maliki school differed in opinion, setting the age of *baligh* at 17 (Noor, 2013).

Based on the above discussions, it is important to note that a child who is *mumaiyiz* but not *baligh*—which classical jurists often place around 7 years old, though it can vary with maturity—cannot be subjected to *hudud* (fixed) or *qisas* (retaliatory) punishments. Instead, corrective measures such as education, discipline, and moral guidance (*ta’dib*) are applied. The responsibility for such correction lies with the child’s guardians or the community. According to most Muslim jurists, a child attains *mumaiyiz* status at the age of 7 (Ahangar, 2016). In practice, this means there is no real conflict between the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275) and the Penal Code (Cap. 22). By incorporating the concept of *mumaiyiz*, the drafters of the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275) focused not merely on chronological age but on the child’s level of understanding. This approach is commendable today, as it recognises that many children as young as 5

years may display greater maturity in understanding life matters than was common even among 15-year-olds a few decades ago (Ahangar, 2016).

International Legal Standards

There is no clear international standard on the age at which criminal responsibility can reasonably be attributed to a juvenile. While it is widely accepted, in line with Article 1 of the UNCRC, that 18 years marks the boundary between childhood and adulthood, there is no general consensus on the specific minimum age at which children can be held criminally responsible (Dusuki, 2009). Article 40(3)(a) of the UNCRC simply enjoins State Parties to establish “a minimum age below which children shall be presumed not to have the capacity to infringe the penal law”. It is, therefore, essential to give due consideration to the UNCRC and other international instruments, such as the Beijing Rules and the Riyadh Guidelines.

United Nations Conventions on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC)

As mentioned earlier, Article 40(3)(a) of the UNCRC simply enjoins State Parties to establish “a minimum age below which children shall be presumed not to have the capacity to infringe the penal law”. Although the UNCRC does not specify a minimum age, the United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, in its ‘General Comment No. 10’ on juvenile justice, states that a minimum age of criminal responsibility below 12 years is considered internationally (United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2007). The Committee further recommends that the minimum age of criminal responsibility should ideally be set at 14 or 16 years (United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2007).

The Committee on the Rights of the Child interprets Article 40(3) of the UNCRC as an obligation for State Parties to establish MACR. This minimum age implies the following: (i) Children who commit an offence below the MACR cannot be held criminally responsible. Although very young children may have the capacity to violate penal law, if they commit an offence while under the MACR, it is irrefutably presumed that they cannot be formally charged or held accountable in criminal proceedings. However, special protective measures may be taken for these children, if necessary, always prioritising their best interests. (ii) Children who are at or above the MACR at the time of committing an offence, but under 18 years of age, may be formally charged and subjected to criminal proceedings. Nonetheless, all such procedures, including any final decisions, must fully comply with the principles and provisions of the UNCRC.

Despite the discussions above, there is no general consensus among State Parties to the UNCRC regarding the MACR. In the absence of such consensus, significant disparities exist between countries, with the MACR ranging widely from as low as 7 to as high as 18 years old (Mousavi et. al, 2015). Consequently, different legal systems internationally set the MACR anywhere between 7 and 18 years. For example, in England and Wales, children under the age of 10 are considered completely exempt from criminal responsibility. In contrast, in Brunei Darussalam, the equivalent age is under 7, as established by section 82 of the Penal Code (Cap. 22).

Other International Instruments

Apart from the UNCRC, which is a key international instrument addressing the issue of the MACR, it is equally important to consider other international instruments such as the Beijing Rules (1985) and the Riyadh Guidelines (1990).

Beijing Rules (1985)

Adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in November 1985, the Beijing Rules marked a significant milestone in the growing international recognition of children’s rights. They were the first international instrument to provide comprehensive guidelines specifically for the administration of

juvenile justice. Serving as a precursor to the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Beijing Rules established essential groundwork for how legal systems around the world should handle cases involving children.

Beijing Rule 4 grants member states the discretion to determine the age of criminal responsibility, taking into account their own cultural and historical contexts (Gupta, 2021). The modern approach, however, emphasises assessing whether a child possesses the moral and psychological capacity for criminal accountability—that is, whether the child can be held responsible for antisocial behavior based on their own judgment and understanding (Gupta, 2021). The notion of responsibility would lose its meaning if the age of criminal responsibility were set too low or if there were no minimum age limit at all. Generally, the concept of responsibility for delinquent or criminal behavior is closely intertwined with other social rights and responsibilities (Gupta, 2021).

In line with Rule 4 of the Beijing Rules, the Committee on the Rights of the Child has recommended State Parties not to set a MACR at a too low level and to increase the existing low MACR to an internationally acceptable level. Based on these recommendations, it can be concluded that a MACR below the age of 12 years is considered by the Committee not to be internationally acceptable. State Parties are encouraged to increase their lower MACR to the age of 12 years as the absolute minimum age and continue to increase it to a higher age level (United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2007).

Riyadh Guidelines (1990)

The United Nations Guidelines for the Prevention of Juvenile Delinquency, known as the Riyadh Guidelines, were adopted by the General Assembly in December 1990 through Resolution 45/112. These guidelines establish a framework aimed at preventing juvenile delinquency, highlighting the significance of community-based services and programmes. Although the Riyadh Guidelines do not set a specific minimum age of criminal responsibility, they emphasize the importance of policies that avoid criminalising or penalising children for conduct that does not cause significant harm to their development or to others.

The guidelines promote a child-centred approach to preventing juvenile delinquency, emphasising that such measures should align with international human rights standards, including the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Convention on the Rights of the Child. They also underscore the vital role of community involvement and the establishment of informal social control mechanisms as preferable alternatives to formal judicial proceedings.

While both the Beijing Rules and the Riyadh Guidelines—key United Nations frameworks—address minimum standards for juvenile justice and consider the developmental and maturational aspects of children’s criminal responsibility, neither explicitly sets a MACR. Nearly two decades later, the UNCRC advanced this discussion by declaring that a MACR below 12 years is unacceptable and recommending that member states set the minimum age around 14 to 16 years. Despite this guidance, significant international variation persists, with countries adopting minimum ages both below and above these recommendations (Pillay, 2019). This inconsistency not only creates confusion but also risks children in different parts of the world facing disparate consequences for similar offences (Pillay, 2019).

Comparative Analysis

In addressing the issue of the MACR, it is important to acknowledge that, due to the absence of a general consensus among State Parties to the UNCRC, significant variations in the MACR exist across the globe. For example, in England and Wales, the MACR is set at 10 years, whereas in Brunei Darussalam it is set at 7 years. This is by virtue of section 83 of the Penal Code (Cap. 22). However, the MACR in Brunei Darussalam, set at 7 years, must be understood as well in conjunction with the provisions of the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275). This diversity underscores the importance of engaging in a comparative analysis of MACR frameworks, including those in ASEAN member states, common law jurisdictions, civil law

jurisdictions, and perspectives rooted in Islamic law—particularly considering the distinctive features of Brunei Darussalam’s dual criminal justice system.

ASEAN and Regional Comparison

While the paper primarily focuses on Brunei Darussalam’s MACR, as reflected in its title, it also extends the analysis to the broader ASEAN context. In doing so, it compares the MACR in Malaysia, Singapore, Indonesia, and the Philippines. Due to the absence of a general consensus among State Parties to the UNCRC regarding the MACR, it is inevitable that the MACR across ASEAN countries varies, as discussed below.

Malaysia

In Malaysia, the MACR is provided by section 82 and section 83 of the Penal Code. For purpose of criminal liability, there are three different stages of children involved namely, section 82 of the Penal Code: complete immunity when a child is below the age of 10 years old; section 83 of the Penal Code: partial immunity when the child is between the age of 10 to 12 years old; and the children above the age of 12 (Mousavi et. al, 2013). In section 82, the child below the age of 10 years old is exempted from criminal responsibility, because it is assumed that children below the age of 10 years old are incapable of understanding the nature and the consequence of their act. The section provides an absolute protection for children under the age of 10 years old. In contrast, section 83 offers partial protection for children above 10 years of age and under the age of 12.

Under the Malaysian Penal Code, the MACR is 10 years. Children aged 10 to under 12 who lack sufficient maturity may be exempt from liability and, if charged, can raise the defence of “infancy.” For criminal responsibility purposes, both this age group and those aged 12 and above are deemed adults, with the latter always treated as such regardless of the offence. However, children above 12 are still subject to distinct criminal procedures and sentencing options compared to adult offenders.

Singapore

Sections 82 and 83 of the Singapore Penal Code confer immunity from criminal liability on children below the age of 12, classifying them into two distinct age groups. The first group comprises children under 10 years of age, who are accorded absolute immunity from criminal prosecution. The second group consists of children aged between 10 and 12, whose immunity is conditional upon the absence of sufficient mental capacity at the time of the alleged offence. In the latter case, the degree of maturity and understanding demonstrated during the commission of the act becomes a pivotal factor, as the requisite *mens rea* cannot be established in the absence of actual knowledge on the part of the child.

In Singapore, the MACR is 10 years. A child below this age cannot be held criminally liable for any conduct, even if it would otherwise constitute an offence. Although the MACR is set at 10, children aged between 10 and 12 who lack sufficient maturity to understand the nature and consequences of their conduct are likewise exempt from criminal liability. In such cases, the courts determine—based on the specific circumstances—whether the child had attained the requisite level of maturity to be found guilty of an offence.

Previously, the MACR was set at 7 years of age. However, Singapore raised it to 10 years through an amendment to the Penal Code (Criminal Law Reform Act 2019). A balance must be maintained between safeguarding the public and ensuring fairness to young children who may lack the maturity to comprehend the consequences of their actions. Singapore viewed its previous MACR as a colonial legacy in need of reform.

Indonesia

The age limit for children’s criminal responsibility in Indonesia has evolved from the provisions of the Criminal Code (KUHP) to Law No. 3 of 1997 on Juvenile Courts, and later to Law No. 11 of 2012 on the Juvenile Criminal Justice System (UUSPPA). This shift is underpinned by philosophical, juridical, and

historical considerations. Under Law No. 3 of 1997, a child is deemed criminally responsible upon reaching the age of 8 but not yet 18, provided they have never been married.

Like Singapore, Indonesia also raised its minimum age of criminal responsibility (MACR). Under Law Number 11 of 2012 on the Juvenile Criminal Justice System, the MACR was set at 12 years, applying to individuals under 18 years of age. The change was guided by several philosophical considerations, including the view that adolescence is a critical stage in a child's development, during which they remain highly susceptible to environmental influences [18]. The law also emphasises restorative justice and diversion measures, which are considered more appropriate in the juvenile justice context to prevent the stigmatisation of children in conflict with the law (Kaluku et. al, 2023).

Philippines

Republic Act No. 9344, or the "Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act of 2006," exempts children who are 15 years old or younger at the time of the offense from criminal liability. However, they are not exempt from civil liability. Instead, such children are subject to intervention programmes referred to as "Bahay Pag-Asa," which is a government-run youth detention and support center (Barredo & Labrador, n.d).

A child above 15 years but below 18 years of age is exempt from criminal liability but not from civil liability. Such a child shall be subjected to an intervention programme unless they acted with discernment, in which case appropriate legal proceedings shall apply (Barredo & Labrador, n.d). Children in conflict with the law may undergo either a diversion programme instead of formal court proceedings or be transferred to a "Bahay Pag-Asa" (an intensive juvenile intervention and support center) during the court process.

The Philippines MACR of 15 years, as established by Republic Act No. 9344 and reaffirmed by Republic Act No. 10630 of 2013. Although there have been periodic political efforts to lower this age to 12 or even 9, none have succeeded (Respicio & Co., 2025). The current framework combines exemption from criminal prosecution with mandatory intervention programmes, applies conditional liability to older minors based on their discernment, and includes a comprehensive range of restorative measures.

While challenges persist in terms of implementation, funding, and public perception, the Philippine approach generally aligns with evolving international standards that favor higher ages of criminal responsibility and prioritise child-centered justice (Respicio & Co., 2025). The future focus should not be on lowering the MACR, but rather on strengthening the social, educational, and rehabilitative systems that ensure juvenile justice protects children while also addressing the needs of victims and communities.

From the foregoing discussions, it is evident that the MACR varies across the selected ASEAN countries, despite the absence of any scientific basis for such discrepancies. There is likewise no evidence of significant cultural differences in child development that could justify the observed legislative or policy variations. Rather, the lack of a standardised MACR appears to arise from: (i) the absence of consensus on the precise definitions of criminal capacity and criminal responsibility; (ii) the lack of conclusive evidence identifying the developmental stage at which such capacity is attained; and (iii) the inherent challenges in assessing this capacity in children who come into conflict with the law (Pillay, 2019).

Common Law Jurisdictions

Under common law jurisdictions, this paper has examined the MACR in England and Wales, Australia, and Canada. The discussion reveals that there is no uniform MACR among these countries. For instance, both England and Wales and Australia set the MACR at 10 years, whereas in Canada it is 12 years.

England and Wales

The MACR in England and Wales is currently set at 10 years (Children and Young Persons Act 1963). A child below this age cannot be found guilty of a criminal offence. Prior to 1998, the common law recognised the doctrine of *doli incapax*, which presumed that children under 14 were incapable of distinguishing between right and wrong and were therefore not criminally responsible. This presumption

was rebuttable, allowing the prosecution to prove that the child understood their conduct was seriously wrong, rather than merely naughty or mischievous.

The *doli incapax* presumption was abolished by section 34 of the Crime and Disorder Act 1998 and is no longer in operation. Consequently, children aged 10 to 13 are now treated by the criminal law in the same way as those aged 14 and above. With the MACR set at 10, England and Wales have the lowest threshold of criminal responsibility in Europe (Pierpoint, 2020).

England and Wales have faced consistent criticism from the Committee on the Rights of the Child for maintaining a MACR of 10 years (Crofts, 2009). Current insights into children's developmental capacities and their rights demonstrate that such a low threshold is inconsistent with international standards.

Australia

In all Australian jurisdictions, the statutory MACR is 10 years. For children aged 10 to 14, a rebuttable presumption—known in common law as *doli incapax*—applies, presuming that the child is incapable of committing a criminal offence. This presumption can be rebutted only if the prosecution proves that, at the relevant time, the child was able to adequately distinguish between right and wrong. Children aged 14 to 17 or 18, depending on the jurisdiction, may be held fully responsible for their criminal acts but remain subject to a distinct set of criminal sanctions, separate from those applied to adult offenders (Warner, 1997). It is important to note that the MACR in Australia is low compared with other countries (Australian Human Rights Commission, 2019).

Given that the MACR in Australia is also relatively low, raising it would create a constructive space to consider responses to young children's needs that do not rely on criminalisation, which carries both short- and long-term negative consequences (Gibbon & O'Brien, 2019). This shift would enable a more meaningful discussion on the most appropriate approaches for children who often experience a range of challenges, including trauma, mental health difficulties, and cognitive impairments.

Canada

In 1983, Canada enacted the Young Offenders Act, raising the MACR from 7 to 12 to protect elementary school-aged children from involvement in the justice system. The Act remained in effect from 1984 to 2003 (Young Offenders Act 1984). In 2004, Canada introduced the Youth Criminal Justice Act, which implemented a range of justice reforms while maintaining the minimum age of 12 and enhancing supports for children and adolescents outside the justice system (Youth Criminal Justice Act, 2002). In Canada, as in many nations, the minimum age threshold has been subject to debate and alteration (Abrams et. al, 2018). For example, while the UNCRC's 2019 updated recommendations called for a MACR of at least 14, Canada chose to retain its MACR at 12 (United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2019).

Civil Law Jurisdictions

When addressing the issue of the MACR, it is important to also examine civil law jurisdictions as part of a comparative doctrinal analysis with Brunei Darussalam. In this regard, this section of the discussion focuses on Germany and France, both of which maintain comparatively higher MACR standards.

Germany

In Germany, the MACR is 14 years (German Criminal Code 1871). Children below this age cannot be held criminally liable, although they may still bear civil liability for any damage they cause. For those aged 14 and above, criminal responsibility arises only if the child demonstrates sufficient moral and mental maturity at the time of the offence to comprehend the unlawfulness of their conduct and to act in accordance with that understanding (Papadodimitraki, 2016) (Weijers, 2016).

The debate surrounding the proposal to lower the MACR in Germany below 14 years remains highly contentious. Proponents argue that earlier criminal interventions are essential to prevent the emergence of criminal trajectories (Schroder, 2025). Conversely, critics warn of the risks of stigmatisation and advocate for preventive and educational measures as more effective alternatives (Schroder, 2025). Consequently, it is necessary to pursue a balanced approach that aligns with international standards.

France

In France, the MACR is 13 years. Children below this age cannot be prosecuted or held criminally liable for their actions, irrespective of the offence committed. Minors aged 13 to 18 are subject to criminal responsibility (French Penal Code 1992); however, they are processed through a specialised juvenile justice system that prioritises rehabilitation over punitive measures.

The French Juvenile Criminal Code further establishes a rebuttable presumption that children under 13 lack the capacity for judgment, while those aged 13 and older are presumed to possess it. It is noteworthy that, as a civil law jurisdiction, France generally establishes a higher MACR than the common law countries examined in this paper.

Islamic Law Perspective

The discussion on the minimum age of criminal responsibility (MACR) from a Syariah perspective revolves around the concepts of *mumaiyiz* and *baligh*. For instance, the actions of a child who is not *mumaiyiz* are not regarded as offences. Conversely, the actions of a child who is *mumaiyiz* but not yet *baligh* may incur punishments, though these would be limited to forms other than *hadd* or *qisas*.

As mentioned earlier, a child's *baligh* status may be determined either naturally, through customary practices, or by setting a maximum age for its attainment. The appearance of physiological signs signifies that the child has entered the stage of adulthood, indicating readiness for independent decision-making and sound judgment. The physical signs for boys include experiencing *al-ibtīlam*, the emission of seminal fluid, and while for girls, it is the onset of menstruation (Noor, 2013).

The determination of whether a child has reached *baligh* (puberty) based on physical signs generally does not present significant difficulties. The greater challenge lies in setting a maximum age in cases where such physical signs are absent. For example, Saudi Arabia currently sets the MACR at 12 years, whereas it was previously set at 7 years. By contrast, Article 49 of the Penal Code of the Islamic Republic of Iran exempts children from criminal responsibility. However, its accompanying note defines a child as someone who has not yet reached the age of puberty (*bulugh*) as prescribed by Shariah. According to the 1991 Civil Code, this threshold is set at 15 lunar years for boys and 9 lunar years for girls.

The paper observes that the application of the MACR within the framework of Islamic law is marked by inconsistencies, particularly with respect to gender distinctions and the type of offence committed. These disparities highlight the pressing need for comprehensive legal reforms to guarantee that all children are treated equitably under the law.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The discussion of the MACR within Brunei Darussalam's dual criminal justice system must be examined from two perspectives: the Penal Code (Cap. 22) and the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275). Under the Penal Code (Cap. 22), the MACR is fixed at 7 years. Meanwhile, under the Syariah Penal Code (Cap. 275), most Muslim jurists consider a child to attain the status of *mumaiyiz* at the age of 7. As mentioned earlier, though the UNCRC does not specify a minimum age, the United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, in its 'General Comment No. 10' on juvenile justice, states that a minimum age of criminal responsibility below 12 years is considered internationally unacceptable (United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2007). The Committee further recommends that the minimum age of criminal responsibility should ideally be set at 14 or 16 years (United Nations Committee on the Rights of the Child, 2007). The paper recommends that, in the interest of the juvenile criminal justice system, Brunei Darussalam's penal laws be aligned with the spirit of section 2 of the Children and Young Persons Act 2006 (Cap. 219), which defines a "child" as a person who has not yet reached 14 years of age. The same section defines a "young person" as someone who has attained 14 years but not yet 18 years. Additionally, section 2 of the Child Order 2000 defines a "child" as a person under 18 years of age. Based on this analysis, the paper recommends raising the MACR to 14 years. This approach would be consistent with the UNCRC's recommendation that the MACR ideally be set at 14 or 16 years. Therefore, harmonising

the MACR across Brunei Darussalam's legal systems is essential for the effective administration of the juvenile criminal justice system, particularly concerning the age of criminal responsibility. The paper also recommends the codification of the Syariah concepts of *tamyiz* (discernment) and *baligh* (puberty) to ensure legal clarity and consistency.

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